

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF EUPHORBIA SEQUIERIANA NECK

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Annotation.

To study the ellagitannins of the plants genus *Euphorbia* - *Euphorbia sequieriana* Neck. Theod growing in Uzbekistan, plant samples were collected in the flowering phase and and at the end of the vegetative period, dried in the shade. The amounts of polyphenolic compounds were isolated from various plant organs (roots, leaves, stems) by successive extraction with 70% aqueous acetone, condensation of the obtained aqueous acetone fractions under vacuum, treatment of aqueous residues with chloroform, ethyl acetate, and addition of hexane to the concentrated ethyl acetate extracts. It was found that polyphenols accumulate mainly in the roots of plants, where their amount is 3.7% (*E. sequieriana* Neck). In leaves, their content ranges from 1.4-2.1%, and in stems 0.08-0.09%. Qualitative reactions, as well as PC and TLC methods, in the composition of the total polyphenols revealed the presence of compounds belonging to the class of flavonols, phenolic acids and tannins. The structures of these compounds were established with the help of physicochemical and spectral data. From the studied organs of these plants, more than 8 phenolic compounds were isolated, 1 of which turned out to be new substances previously not described in the literature.

Key words.

polyphenols, ellagitannins, galloyl group, hexahydroxydiphenoyl group, valoneyl group; ¹³C NMR spectroscopy; Q-TOF LC-MS. Key words: *polyphenols, ellagitannins, galloyl group, hexahydroxydiphenoyl group, valoneoyl group, ¹³C NMR spectroscopy; Q-TOF LC-MS.*

Introduction

Among the most important classes of natural compounds that determine the therapeutic effect of medicinal plants, polyphenols occupy a significant place. A

wide range of biological effects and low toxicity put them in a number of promising compounds in this regard. Therefore, the search for plants containing polyphenols, the development of methods for their selection, establishing their chemical structure and studying the dependence of biological activity on the chemical structure in order to create new effective medicines is an important and urgent problem of modern bioorganic chemistry.

Elagotannins are the largest vegetable polyphenols among hydrolyzed tannins. They are complex esters of elagoic acid and sugars. To date, more than 700 individual connections have been identified and installed. Elagotannins have a wide range of biological activity, of which the most important are antiviral, antitumor and immunomodulatory effects. In fact, the development of elagotannin chemistry over the past decades makes them from the most underestimated class one of the most promising. Recent advances in the field of NMR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry have identified complex mixtures of tannins with different molecular weight and a degree of gallolination [1-4]. In addition, these methods are ideal for characterizing oligomers and are considered suitable methods for analyzing tannins with great structural inhomogeneity.

Based on the foregoing, we investigated the polyphenols of *Euphorbia sequieriana* Neck plants. Of these, more than 8 phenolic compounds were identified and their chemical structure was established, and the biological activity of some of them was revealed. It was revealed that a number of them are new substances not previously described in the literature. Using physicochemical and spectral data, the structures of these compounds are established.

Experimental part

Crushed and dried aboveground and underground organs of plants, *Euphorbia sequieriana* Neck., collected during the flowering period and at the end of the vegetative period, growing in the mountainous areas of the Namangan region, the Republic of Uzbekistan served as a source of raw materials.

To isolate tannins, dried and crushed plant material was extracted with 70% aqueous acetone. The aqueous acetone extract was concentrated on a rotary evaporator. The resulting aqueous residue was treated with chloroform to remove lipophilic substances. Then the aqueous residue was extracted with ethyl acetate. By thickening the ethyl acetate extract under vacuum, adding a fourfold volume of hexane to the condensed extracts, and filtering the precipitated precipitates, the amounts of polyphenols were obtained.

The sums of polyphenols were chromatographed on silica gel in chloroform-methanol solvent systems (17:3; 17:4; 17:5) and 3 fractions were isolated. Known

phenoloxo acids were isolated from the first fraction. in the second fraction, the presence of compounds related to flavonols was observed, and in the third fraction, tannins.

Separation of tannins was carried out by column chromatography on silica gel brand LS 100/40 (Czechoslovakia) (solvent system 60% methanol, ethyl acetate). To identify and determine the homogeneity of substances, TLC was used on Silufol UV-254 plates (eluent benzene:acetone, 9:4). To determine the composition and establish the structure of new substances, methylation, methanolysis, acid and stepwise hydrolysis were carried out [5-7].

Results and discussion.

For the isolation of polyphenols, plant samples were collected in the flowering phase and at the end of the vegetative period and dried in the shade. Extraction of various plant organs (roots, leaves, stems) with 70% aqueous acetone, condensation of aqueous acetone fractions under vacuum, successive repeated treatment of aqueous residues with chloroform and ethyl acetate, distillation of ethyl acetate fractions, addition of hexane to the condensed ethyl acetate extracts, the amounts of polyphenolic compounds were isolated . It was revealed that polyphenols accumulate mainly in the roots of plants, where their amount is 3.7% (*E. sequieriana* Neck.). In leaves, their content ranges from 1.4-2.1%, and in stems 0.08-0.09%.

Qualitative reactions in the composition of the sum of polyphenols revealed the presence of compounds belonging to the class of flavonols, phenolic acids and tannins. Using paper chromatography, it was shown that the polyphenols of individual organs almost do not differ from each other in terms of their qualitative composition, but differ in the quantitative content of individual components. So if flavonols make up a large part of the total polyphenols of leaves, then tannins are the main components of the total of polyphenols of plant roots. Therefore, we continued further studies on the compounds of plant roots, where the largest amount of polyphenols is localized. Three fractions were isolated by chromatography of the total polyphenols of plant roots on silica gel columns in chloroform-methanol (17:3; 17:4; 17:5) solvent systems. Paper chromatography revealed that the first fraction contains phenolic acids (n-butanol-acetic acid-water 4:1:5 - Rf 0.51 gallic acid; toluene: ethyl acetate: methanol: formic acid 10:9:6:5 - Rf 0.72 ellagic acid) , the second - flavonols, the third - tannins. The phenolic compounds contained in the second fraction were chromatographed on a polyamide column. Chloroform-methanol (9:1; 8:2) systems were used as eluent, and individual compounds were isolated. Comparison of the results of

physicochemical research methods with the data given in the literature revealed that these substances are known flavonols - kaempferol, quercetin, kaempferol-3-glucoside. There are much more of these compounds in the aerial parts of plants than in the roots. After rechromatography of the third fraction in various solvent systems on a silica gel column, a number of individual compounds were isolated. With the help of physico-chemical research methods, their structure was established. Along with tannins known from the literature data (2,3-di-O-galloyl- β -D-glucose, geranium), one new (1) substance not previously described in the literature was isolated from the studied plant species.

Compound 1 - isolated from *Euphorbia sequieriana* Neck., white amorphous powder. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -200 (c 1.0, MeOH); UV spectrum (EtOH, λ_{max} , nm): 220, 280; MS m/z: 1117 [M-H]⁻.

To determine the composition and establish the structure, substance 1 was subjected to a series of chemical transformations according to scheme 1. Glucose (2), gallic (3), and ellagic acids (4) were found in the products of acid hydrolysis with 5% H₂SO₄. Methylation of the substance with dimethyl sulfate and anhydrous K₂CO₃ leads to the formation of permethylate, after alkaline hydrolysis with a methanolic solution of sodium methoxide, methyl tri-O-methylgallate (5) was formed (TLC, R_f 0.75, solvent system-3: benzene-acetone 4:1) and dimethyl - hexamethoxydiphenate (6) (TLC, R_f 0.36, system-1). In the products of partial hydrolysis of substance 1 (heating in water at 90°C), 1-O-trigalloyl- β -D-glucopyranose (7) and ellagic acid glucoside (8) are formed.

Scheme 1. Chemical transformations of compound-1

In the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of substance 1, obtained under conditions of complete suppression of the spin-spin interaction with protons, signals characteristic of glucose, gallic and ellagic acids are detected (Table 1) [8-12].

Table 1

Chemical shifts (δ , 100 MHz, acetone $-d_6$ + D_2O , ppm) of carbon atom signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of substance 1

atoms C	Trigalloyl-gr.			GGDF-gr.		Glucose	
						I	II
C-1	120.4	120.4	120.4	115.5	115.8	93.6	96.5
C-2	110.1	110.1	110.1	125.8	126.4	6.7	74.2
C-3	145.9	145.9	145.9	107.8	108.1	75.2	73.0
C-4	139.3	139.3	139.3	145.8	145.8	69.6	69.6
C-5	145.9	145.9	145.9	136.6	136.4	74.3	75.1
C-6	110.1	110.1	110.1	144.4	144.5	63.2	63.4
C-7	168.8	166.3	164.4	167.6	168.0		

Intense signals at 93.6 and 96.5 ppm related to C-1 carbon atoms indicate that ellagitannin contains two sugar residues at which the anomeric centers have the β -configuration. Shift to a stronger field and manifestation in the region 93.6, 76.7, 63.4 ppm signals related to the C-1 and C-2 atoms of the first glucose center and C-6 of the second glucose center indicate acylation of carbohydrate residues at these positions.

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum contains signals of three residues of gallic acid: signals of carbon atoms of carbonyl groups at 164.4, 166.3, 168.8 ppm, and the signal C-1 of carbon atoms of the trigalloyl group is observed at 120.4 ppm. Signals of carbon atoms C-2 and C-6, as well as C-3 and C-5, coincide and give relatively intense signals at 110.1 and 145.9 ppm, respectively. The C-4 carbon atom of this residue is screened and, as a result of the diamagnetic shift, resonates at 139.3 ppm. The spectrum also contains signals from 14 carbon atoms of the hexahydroxydiphenoyl group. An analysis of the chemical shifts of the carbon atoms of the hexahydroxydiphenoyl (HGDP) group shows that in the molecule of substance 1, two glucose atoms are linked to each other using the GGDP group. Substituted carbon atoms of the HGDP group C-4, C-4', C-5, C-5' and C-6, C'-6 resonate at 145.8, 136.4-136.6 and 144.4-144.5 ppm, respectively. Unsubstituted carbon atoms C-3 and C-3' appear in the region of 107.8 and 108.1 ppm. The signals of C-7 and C-7' carbon atoms of carbonyl groups give intense signals at 167.6 and 168.0 ppm.

Scheme 2. Possible ways of substance fragmentation 1

These data are confirmed by the mass spectrometric decay data of substance 1 obtained on an LC-MS Q-TOF instrument under negative ionization. As can be seen from Scheme 2, a molecular ion with m/z 1117 ($[M-H]^-$) splits into two fragments with m/z 635 and 481. This indicates a break in the ester bond between two glucose molecules associated with hexahydroxydiphenoyl and tri-halo fragments [11-12].

The presence of a signal at m/z 635 in the mass spectrum indicates the esterification of glucose by trigallic acid, while the signals at m/z 481 and 429 indicate fragmentation of ellagic acid associated with glucose. The secondary ion with m/z 635 is further split into fragments with m/z 169, 153 and 125, which correspond to the standard gallic acid fragmentation pathway. Negative ions with m/z 301 and 153 correspond to the detachment of the hexahydroxydiphenoyl and halo fragment from the molecule, which is consistent with the literature data [2-3]. The presence in the mass spectrum of an intense fragmentation ion signal with m/z 301, formed during the decay of a secondary ion with m/z 481, indicates that substance 1 contains ellagic acid.

Based on the analysis of chemical products and spectral constants and their

comparison with the literature data, it was found that substance 1 is a diester of hexahydroxydiphenoyl-6-(O-β-D-glucopyranoside)-2-(O-1-O-trigalloyl-β-D-glucopyranoside) (8).

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Conclusions: The polyphenols of *E.sequieriana* Neck plant roots have been studied. growing in Uzbekistan. It was revealed that polyphenols accumulate mainly in the roots of plants, where their amount is 3.7% (*E. sequieriana* Neck.). More than 8 compounds have been isolated from the studied plant species, including 3 flavonoids, 2 phenolic acids, and 3 hydrolysable tannins. Along with known polyphenolic compounds, one (1) new hydrolyzable tannin - diester of hexahydroxydiphenoyl-6-(O-β-D-glucopyranoside)-2-(O-1-O-trigalloyl-β-D-glucopyranoside) (*Euphorbia sequieriana* Neck .) With the help of physicochemical and spectral data, the structures of these compounds were established.

REFERENCES:

1. Es-Safi N., Guyot S., Ducrot P. NMR, ES/MS, and MALDI-TOF/MS analysis of pear juice polymeric proanthocyanidins with potent free radical scavenging activity // . J. Agric.Food Chem. 2006, 54, 6969-6977. doi:[10.1021/jf061090f](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf061090f)
2. Zhang L., Lin Y. HPLC, NMR and MALDI-TOF MS analysis of condensed tannins from *Lithocarpus glaber* leaves with potent free radical scavenging activity // Molecules. 2008. V.4 (12), P. 2986-97. doi: [10.3390/molecules13122986](https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules13122986).

3. Chen Y., Hagerman A.E. Characterization of soluble non-covalent complex between bovine serum albumin and [beta]-1, 2, 3, 4, 6-penta-O-galloyl-D-glucopyranose by MALDI-TOF MS J// J. Agric Food Chem . 2004. V.16 (12), P. 4008-4011. doi: 10.1021/jf035536t.

4. Tanguchi S., Imayoshi Y., Yoshida T., Hatano T. A new trimeric hydrolyzable tannin, oenotherin T₂, isolated from aerial parts of *Oenothera tetraptera* Cav. // Heterocycles. 2009. V.79. P. 617-626. <http://id.ndl.go.jp/bib/000000129276>

5. № IAP 06574 Средство, блокирующее протеазу 3CLpro и РНК-полимеразу RdRp РНК вирусов// Салихов Ш.И. Ажайкебаер АИСА, Ёпгшап SHEN, Yechun XU, Huaqiang XU, Gengfu XIAO, Xiaogruo JIANG, Leike ZHANG, Зиявитдинов Ж.Ф, Ощепкова Ю.И., Мирзаахмедов Ш.Я., Абдулладжанова Н.Г., Бердиев Н.Ш.

6. Amakura Y., Yoshida T. Tannins and Related Polyphenols of *Euphorbiaceae* Plants. XIV. Euphorbin I, a New Dimeric Hydrolyzable Tannin from *Euphorbia watanabei* // Chem. Pharm. Bull. 1996, V. 44 (7), P. 1803-1807.

doi:10.1248/cpb.42.1803

7. Yoshida T., Amakura Y., Liu Y-Z., Okuda T. Tannins and Related Polyphenols of *Euphorbiaceae* Plants. XI. Three New Hydrolyzable Tannins and a Polyphenol Glucoside from *Euphorbia humifusa* // Chem. Pharm. Bull. 1994 V. 42 (9). P.1803-1807. doi.org/10.1248/cpb.42.1803.

8. Santos-Buelga C., Williamson G. Methods in polyphenol analysis // The Royal Society of Chemistry. Cambridge, UK. 2003.-P.33-38. doi.org/10.1021/np030739x

9. Yoshida T., Hatano T., Okuda T., Memon M.U., Shingu T., Inoue K. Spectral and chromatographic analyses of tannins. I. ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance spectra of hydrolysable tannins // Chem. Pharm. Bull. 1984. - V. 32. -P. 1790-1799.

10. Hatano T., Yoshida T., Shingu T., Okuda T. ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance spectra of hydrolysable tannins. III. Tannins having ¹³C₄ glucose and C-glucosidic Linkage//Chem.Pharm.Bull.1988.-V.36.-P.3849-3856.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1248/cpb.36.3849>

11. Rakhimov R.N, Abdulladzhanova N.G., Kamaev F.G. Phenolic compounds from *Euphorbia franchetii* (B.Fedtsch) and *Euphorbia canescens* (L) // Chemistry of Natural Compounds 2011. V. 47. №2. P. 286-287.

12. Rakhimov R.N, Qodirova Sh.O, Abdulladjanova N.G, Ziyayev D.A, Komilov Q.O, // Elmurodov B, Shamuratov B.A, Ziyavitdinov J.F.Elucidation of structures of new ellagitannins from plants of *Euphorbiaceae* // Journal of

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DOI:[10.31838/jcr.07.03.81](https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.03.81)